

DEVELOPMENT OF ACOUSTIC PARAMETER CALCULATION TOOL FOR BIM SUPPORTING SOFTWARE PACKAGE

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Abstract: In the following paper the initial phases of the preparation for computational tool enabling the calculation of acoustic parameters for Building Information Modeling (BIM), supporting architectural design tools will be presented. The goal is to use the opportunities provided by a BIM model and use the 3D model and also information stored to evaluate basic acoustic performance parameters, such as the calculation of the average sound absorption coefficient. Attention is paid to maintaining the interoperability between the model set up and calculation process. Firstly the limitations of BIM design tools and current state-of-the art parameter set up will be defined. Secondly, existing tools, fully or partially using BIM provided information, for calculation of acoustic parameters will be described. Their functionality and interoperability with BIM design tools will be defined. The results of the state-of-the art analysis will be used for the benchmarking of the developed tool for acoustic calculations. Thirdly, possible design structures and the expected functionality of the developed tool will be described. Lastly, a mock-up version and current functionality of the developed tool will be presented.

Key words: building information modeling, acoustic parameters, calculation tool

1. Introduction

Building Information Modeling (BIM) is a central information platform to support the integration and analysis of data, wherein all the project data is stored in a single data repository. BIM enables gathering of data for defined elements, storing information about their geometry, position, design, parametric performance and other relevant data necessary for support of construction, fabrication, performance evaluation and procurement activities [1.]. The implementation is supported (mandatory in certain countries) by local authority offices [2.], and the BIM methodologies are being Standardized and also implemented in legislation.

In this paper we will present the constrains of developing a computational tool enabling calculation of acoustic parameters in a BIM supporting modeling platform. The goal was to identify a suitable platform and to use the already available 3D model information, establish a live connection between acoustic calculation and 3D modeling. The tool strives to enable a smoother and dynamic designing process where the necessity of integration of the 3D model into a dedicated third-party acoustic simulation software would be completely omitted, and to enable quick comparison of design variants.

1.1. Limitations of BIM software and selection

BIM modeling in recent years has seen one of the highest increases in the engagement of architecture, engineering and construction (AEC) professionals, and has undergone one of the most promising developments in the industry. BIM modeling supports cooperation of professionals involved in project drafting and realization, and supports the development of sustainable building facilities. The final model is data rich, representing a full virtual 3D model of the developed construction, storing parametric data including dimensions, design, costs, physical properties of elements, description of relationships between objects, as well as life-cycle information. BIM modeling has the potential to minimize the fragmentation of the building design process, enabling inclusive involvement of large groups of stakeholders ranging from design, construction, operation, and maintenance, having beneficial impact on clash detection, cost effectiveness and overall sustainability [3., 4.].

To the identified most often used BIM software packages by architects and civil engineers belong:

- Revit (Autodesk) [5.];
- Bentley Architecture and its products (Bentley) [6.];
- ArchiCAD (Graphisoft) [7.];
- Allplan (Nemetschek) [8.].

Whereas all of the above-mentioned software enable multidisciplinary and collaborative design process to create intelligent structure models in coordination with

other building components, internally all the input data is stored differently, in proprietary data formats. This means all external applications need to be developed in a compliant language (specific to each individual software), otherwise they can not be integrated [9. – 11.].

Data derived from different BIM software can be shared among software applications through Industry Foundation Classes (IFC). IFC is a neutral, non-proprietary open international standard for BIM data [12.].

2. Application model options

An application for calculation of acoustic parameters using the data stored in a BIM model can be developed as:

- a plug-in for a dedicated BIM software platform;
- a plug-in developed in a graphical algorithmic modeling platform extension for a BIM software package;
- as an autonomous software using imported BIM data.
- hybrid solutions

All these options have their own advantages and disadvantages based on the limitation of their functionality, development complexity and interoperability of the interchanged data.

2.1. A plug-in for a dedicated BIM software platform

To extend the core functionality of BIM software, Revit and ArchiCAD allow you to program with a compliant language an extension plug-in, which is then after installation available in Add-Ins External Tools toolbar. The program would have to consist of BIM data extraction module, and calculation module.

This method has following advantages:

- easy to use – the plug-in is fully integrated into the BIM software platform, no need to get to know a new platform;
- the interoperability is looped – changes in architecture can be immediately verified by the tool;
- no need to export and import the created BIM model into a separate platform;

the disadvantages:

- limited functionality – the plug-in is limited by the Application Program Interface (API) provided by the proprietary software developer.
- has to be developed for each BIM software separately, based on each proprietary data format.

This type of the application model is best used for quick evaluation of acoustic performance of an indoor space during the schematic building design stage. It enables to quickly verify the impact of various designs and materials. Also in this application version all the acoustic performance parameters of different materials and constructions are stored within the BIM model. However, until now none of the above mentioned BIM software

package does, by default contain acoustic performance data on any element or material.

To the authors knowledge there is no such application yet available for any of the above mentioned BIM software packages.

2.2. A plug-in developed in a graphical algorithmic modeling platform extension for a BIM software package

To develop the plug-in, it is possible to use a graphical scripting platform extension for a BIM software package. This can be for example an application developed in Grasshopper for ArchiCAD [13.] or in Dynamo for Revit [14.].

To the advantages of this solution belongs:

- changes in design will result in changes in simulation – the platforms communicate directly in order to create and manipulate a BIM model in full or in parts through the graphical scripting interface;
- it is not necessary to import the current design into a third-party simulation software;
- the graphical scripting platforms are fully or partially open-source;
- the lightweight scripting interface and the fact that the script is represented visually, no, or minimal programming experiences are required to start.

The disadvantages to be considered:

- the necessity to be familiar with two software platforms;
- for more complex application the graphical representation of the script becomes difficult to manage;
- assigning and storing of acoustic properties is done outside of the BIM software platform.

There is already a plug-in available for acoustics simulation called Pachyderm developed in Grasshopper (by Arthur van der Harten) [15.] and can be used for models created in Rhinoceros or ArchiCAD (uses the geometry data). It enables the use of common geometrical acoustics algorithms. Pachyderm is capable to output data on reverberation time, early decay time, center time, clarity, definition and strength/loudness. No other similar application is available to the authors knowledge.

2.3. An autonomous software using imported BIM data

In this version, relevant data is exported from the BIM model and imported into an autonomous simulation software. This version is the one most commonly used, where a 3D model is imported to a simulation software such as ODEON and EASE [16. – 17.]. The advantages of this model are:

- as a separate simulation engine, the most complex simulations, predictions, visualization and prediction can be enabled;
- if well prepared, the results are the most accurate.

The main disadvantages are:

- most of the available software are only able to import the 3D model geometry, and no parametric performance data can be used from the BIM model;
- the imported geometry has to be altered after import, to make it compatible and fulfill the requirements given by the simulation software;
- material acoustic performance properties have to be added in the simulation software.

Some of the disadvantages could be eliminated if the simulation software would be able to import data in the IFC standard for BIM data. This was enabled only for COMSOL [18.]. The necessary information for acoustic analysis (simulation environment, sound source location, and acoustic absorption coefficient) are extracted from the IFC file through a developed API (application programming interface)

This method has current advantages:

- it enables to quickly import data from BIM model into advanced software for acoustic analysis;
- and disadvantages:
- the interoperability is limited, and the streamline of work is only one direction, no feedback loop between architectural design and acoustical analysis (changes in architecture will not be automatically updated in acoustical analysis).

3. Application design

As our goal was to use the already available 3D model and performance data to enable basic acoustic calculations in the environment of a Building Information Modeling (BIM) software platform, we have decided to develop a plug-in for dedicated BIM software platform, in our case for Revit. This was done based on the following assumptions:

- there does not yet exist (to the authors knowledge) an acoustic performance evaluation plugin for Revit, whereas there is already Pachyderm for Rhinoceros and ArchiCAD [15., 19.];
- Revit has a well-developed support infrastructure, and a broad documentation database, which simplifies the software development [9.];
- Revit is the most used BIM authoring software;
- ArchiCAD plugin development is limited to C and C++ programming language, whereas Revit .NET API enables to use any .NET compliant language including VB.NET, C#, C and C++.
- Similar plug-ins such as Pachyderm will serve as a benchmark.

4. Current state of the plug-in development

We have developed a basic application which enables calculation of average sound absorption coefficient of a room.

Currently the development mainly consists on drafting the work flow, whereas the whole functionality would be provided by a downloadable plug in. Until now, this functionality was already provided:

- Application info note, which loads on start up.
- A dedicated application panel, providing all the functionality of the application.
- By button triggered generation of a shared parameter file with predefined acoustic parameters.
- A command for selecting element faces, and extraction of relevant data such as element name, ID, area, material and shared parameter values.
- A command for extracting data, by picking up a room for evaluation. The data includes definition of boundary elements, with their area, element ID, material, and shared parameter values. This selection tool is an enhanced tool based on a room selection tool developed and made available by Jeremy Tammik [20.]. It handles all the special cases which can arise while modeling the boundary elements of a room. Also the broad variety of bounding elements that can be used.

Further it is necessary to:

- Prepare a dedicated task dialog, which will contain a list of selected faces, and enable selection/deselection of further faces. Enable a lookup and adjustment of relevant data. And enable calculation.
- Resolve the Revit native problem of selecting floors and ceilings. Due to the way floors and ceilings are modeled in Revit, the program is not working with actual real areas of ceilings and floors but is counting them based on the area enclosed by the boundary elements such as walls and windows. If for example a room would have stairs, the area provided would only represent the gross floor plan area, not the actual area of the stairs.
- Provide a data set providing sound absorption coefficient values for standard materials and standard wall structures.
- Calculation process.
- Export of results.

Attention will have to be put, for handling room designs with exceptions, and in cases no material description or insufficient data is provided.

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented the initial phases of preparation and development of a computational tool enabling calculation of acoustic parameters in a BIM supporting modeling platform. The tool strives to enable basic acoustic calculations in the environment of Revit. The goal is to use the already available 3D model, and to establish a live connection between acoustic calculation

and 3D modeling. This will enable a smoother and more dynamic design process where the necessity of integration of the 3D model into acoustic simulation software (such as ODEON) would be completely omitted.

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